

Preliminary results of a new magnetotelluric profile in the Iberian Massif (Central Iberian Zone, Portugal)

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The area of Trancoso-Pinhel (NE of Portugal), located in the Central Iberian Zone (Iberian Massif), has been recently explored in terms of structural mapping and deep geophysical profiling. In this section of the Neoproterozoic and Paleozoic crystalline basement of the Variscan belt affected by polyphasic deformation was recognized for the first time a flat-lying kilometer-scale extensional shear zone (Pinhel shear zone) that was later captured by strike-slip shear zones (Huebra and Juzbado-Penalva do Castelo shear zones) and upright folds (e.g., Tamames-Marofa-Sátão synform).

The aim of this study is to use the magnetotelluric method (MT) to obtain information about the structure in depth of the Trancoso-Pinhel area, thus providing resistivity information from the upper crust, to better delineate the interference of the flat-lying shear zone with later strike-slip shear zones and folds and their relationship with syn-kinematic and post-kinematic plutonic rocks. A total of 18 MT sites were installed along a 30 km-long NNW-SSE profile with 3-5 km inter-site spacing (from Almeida to Figueira de Castelo Rodrigo). This presentation summarizes the preliminary results of the MT survey and the 2D inversion model.

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